

ISM-LATVIA: International student mobility towards off-beat destinations: geography, demographic profile and lived experiences in Latvia

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is prepared in the framework of the Latvian Council of Science Fundamental and Applied Research project No. LZP-2024/1-0556 "International student mobility towards off-beat destinations: geography, demographic profile and lived experiences in Latvia" (project manager: Dr. geogr. Elīna Apsīte-Beriņa, 01.01.2025. - 31.12.2027., 300 000.00 EUR).

Summary of the project:

The field of International Student Mobility (ISM) research has witnessed a significant expansion since the late 1990s. This growth mirrors trends in institutional and policy discussions surrounding the broader internationalisation of education. Scholars have diligently explored the "why," "where," and "how" of educational migration among young adults. This project critiques the extant body of ISM research, highlighting critical blind spots and advocating for a more interdisciplinary approach to address the evolving nature of educational migration on both international and local scales.

Firstly, we contend that a persistent focus on "Westward mobility" and overemphasising "talented youth" in ISM research restricts our understanding of the student body. We propose a broader perspective to capture students' diverse motivations and experiences in educational migration globally. Secondly, the blossoming interest in the geography of higher education offers a new lens for analysis. We propose examining the changing nature of urban neighbourhoods surrounding universities. This includes understanding how these areas connect to broader residential patterns defined by age groups, ethnicities, and place-based identities. Latvia serves as a geographically significant case study country. It represents an "off-beat destination" for ISM while possessing a unique educational landscape. This project will employ a spatial mapping approach to investigate the "spillover effects" of strategies to attract international students and the construction of new campuses. Our analysis will focus on geographic correlations between universities and studentification (the concentration of student populations in specific neighbourhoods). By incorporating these perspectives, this research aims to contribute valuable insights into the evolving dynamics of international student mobility and its impact on urban spaces.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Izp-2024/1-0556

Researchers

Maris Berzins (0000-0002-5773-3307), Girts Burgmanis (orcid:0000-0001-5903-2283), Sindija Balode (0000-0002-6968-512X), Elina Apsite Berina (0000-0001-5537-5879)

Organizations
Univeristy of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: ISM-LATVIA: International student mobility towards off-beat destinations: geography, demographic profile and lived experiences in Latvia

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Contact: Apsīte-Beriņa Elīna (elina.apsite-berina@lu.lv), Svarinskis Artūrs (arturs.svarinskis@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: lzp-2024/1-0556

Project: Cite Project

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Interview materials with international students in Latvia

In this data set interviews with international students in Latvia will be summarised.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection is to explore the motivations and characteristics of international students who choose Riga, Latvia—an "off-beat destination"—for their studies. The research particularly focuses on students who engage in the local labor market, aiming to generate insights into their decision-making process and socio-economic impact on the host country.

Relation to Project Objectives

This data collection directly supports the project's objective of understanding:

The factors influencing international students' choice of Riga as a study destination.

Their integration into the local labor market and broader socio-economic contributions.

The challenges and opportunities they face in terms of education, employment, and social adaptation.

Origin of Data

The data will be obtained through 20 in-depth interviews with international students in Latvia. These interviews will provide qualitative insights into their experiences, motivations, and socio-economic involvement, complementing broader statistical analyses within the project.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No similar, suitable for reuse data have been found

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Data might be helpful to other 1) researchers and 2) scholars who are working on topics related to International Student Mobility; 3) students.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

international students, Latvia, degree students, international student mobility

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org>

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Elina Apsite Berina (0000-0001-5537-5879)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

To ensure data security and compliance with data protection protocols, the scientific team will implement both organizational and technical security measures. These measures will protect the collected data from unauthorized disclosure, destruction, alteration, or loss throughout the project's duration and beyond. Organizational Measures:

A data sharing agreement will govern how data is accessed and used.

Codes of conduct and confidentiality agreements will be followed to uphold ethical standards.

Data access will be restricted to authorized team members, ensuring responsible data handling.

Technical Measures:

Data will be stored on secure servers with password protection and encryption where necessary.

Pseudonymized personal data will be stored separately from code keys for added security.

Locked storage solutions (e.g., drawers, secure offices) will be used for physical data protection.

Regular backups will be maintained in different locations to prevent data loss.

The use of flash drives and portable storage devices will be minimized to reduce security risks.

Data will be preserved in trusted repositories such as Zenodo for long-term storage and curation.

The ISM-Latvia document repository is hosted on the LU OneDrive collaborative platform, with restricted access managed by the Project Coordinator. Work package (WP) leaders are responsible for organizing and maintaining their designated WP folders.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Survey with international students in Latvia

In this data set, survey data with international students studying in Latvia will be summarised.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection is to examine the motivations and characteristics of international students who choose Riga, Latvia, as an "off-beat destination" for their education. A particular focus is placed on students who participate in the local labor market. The goal is to provide new insights into their decision-making processes and their socio-economic impact on the host country.

Relation to Project Objectives

The collected data will contribute to understanding:

Why international students select Riga over other destinations.

Their socio-economic integration, particularly regarding employment.

The broader implications of their presence on the Latvian education system and labor market.

Origin of Data

The data originates from a representative survey conducted among at least 550 international students in Latvia, ensuring stratification by age, gender, and education level. The survey will collect socio-demographic details such as

residence, age, length of stay, gender, and education. Additionally, qualitative insights will be gathered through interviews with international students.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Event
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No similar, suitable for reuse data have been found

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Data might be helpful to other 1) researchers and 2) scholars who are working on topics related to International Student Mobility; 3) students.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

international students, Latvia, degree students, international student mobility

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org>

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Elina Apsite Berina (0000-0001-5537-5879)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall

- Passwords
- Physical access control

To ensure data security and compliance with data protection protocols, the scientific team will implement both organizational and technical security measures. These measures will protect the collected data from unauthorized disclosure, destruction, alteration, or loss throughout the project's duration and beyond. Organizational Measures:

A data sharing agreement will govern how data is accessed and used.

Codes of conduct and confidentiality agreements will be followed to uphold ethical standards.

Data access will be restricted to authorized team members, ensuring responsible data handling.

Technical Measures:

Data will be stored on secure servers with password protection and encryption where necessary.

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Yes

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Co-creation event materials

In this data set with materials from co-creative events with international students, universities' international departments and policy makers will be gathered.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

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Relation to Project Objectives

This data collection directly supports the project's objective of:

Identifying key factors influencing international students' choice of Riga.

Understanding their integration into the local labor market and socio-economic contributions.

Bridging the gap between research and practice by incorporating the perspectives of both practitioners and policymakers at institutional and national levels.

Origin of Data

The data will be obtained through co-creative sessions with two practitioners and policymakers from both institutional and national levels. These sessions will provide valuable insights into how international student mobility is managed, promoted, and supported, offering a practical perspective that complements academic research findings.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

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